

paper Chain

FINAL REPORT ON EVENTS

D9.4 (M44)

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WP9 Communication & Dissemination

Task 9.4

2021, January

New Market Niches For the Pulp and Paper Industry Waste based on Circular Economy Approaches

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0. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document constitutes the final report on events, congresses, conferences within the WP9 “Communication & Dissemination” of the European funded PAPERCHAIN project, under the Grant Agreement 730305. The project kicked off in June 2017 and will be still standing up to June 2021 (48 months). This report is due in the 44th month of the project, corresponding to January 2021.

The content of this deliverable not only reflects the events, but also presents a summary of the communication materials that have been developed. In addition, a list and brief reviews of the publications that have been developed are presented, although this last point will be developed in depth in deliverable D9.5 - Final Data Management Plan.

Throughout the project, the progress of all tasks, including C&D activities, has been evaluated through 3 reporting periods:

- The first periodic report covered the months M1 to M18, where the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D9.1), the Data Management Plan (D9.2) and most of the Communication Materials (D9.3), including their implementation strategy, were elaborated. The Circular Case started to be developed and mainly communication work on the progress of the project was developed, expanding the communication materials made available for C&D activities. This was due to the huge amount of information and developments covered by the project.

- The second periodic report covered 18 months, from M19 to M36, and ended in May 2020. During this period, the results obtained in the first Circular Case developed began to be obtained and presented, which led to a significant increase in the presence of the consortium partners at events, congresses and exhibitions. All the new communication materials made available were used and have served (and are serving) to present the project quickly. The end of this period saw a halt in face-to-face dissemination activities due to the COVID pandemic, which led to a subsequent rethink of the dissemination and communication strategy.

- The third and last reporting period corresponds to the months M37 to M48, with an extension of the project foreseeable due to the pandemic and not confirmed at the date of submission of this report. During this period, most of the attendance at events for the presentation of results was planned, including a series of workshops in the countries where the Circular Cases have been developed. Due to the pandemic, the entire strategy has migrated to digital environments and it has been decided to expand the digital communication materials in order to capture, present and introduce the project prior to the dissemination activities.

This report includes all the events that paperChain partners have attended and a forecast of upcoming events and workshops that will take place in digital environments due to the pandemic.

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Keywords

Events	Congress	Conference	Workshop	Meeting
Communication	Dissemination	Licences	CERIF	Specification

GLOSSARY OF ACRONYMS

WP	Work Package
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
EU	European Union

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1-Introduction and context

1.1 Introduction and context

The present document constitutes the final report on events, congresses, conferences within the WP9 “Communication & Dissemination” of the European funded PAPERCHAIN project, under the Grant Agreement 730305. The project kicked off in June 2017 and will continue until June 2021 (48 months).

Three deliverables have been already performed in the Communication and Dissemination WP:

- **D9.1- Communication and Dissemination Plan (M6)**
- **D9.2- Data Management Plan (M7)**
- **D9.3- Communication Materials (M9)**

Throughout the project, a series of communication materials have been developed for the presentation of the project and the dissemination of its results, adapted to the different event formats attended. A large number of materials and elements have been developed that have unified the consortium's image and have served to introduce the project in a consensual, unique and unequivocal way. For this reason, this report will present the communication materials developed and used in the different events in which the consortium has participated.

This report is due in the 44th month of the project, corresponding to January 2021. The evolution of the different Circular Cases into which the project is divided is progressing appropriately, with Circular Case 4 still pending resolution and the rest of the cases being monitored. According to the initial planning, it was in the last quarter of the period that the project's dissemination activities were planned to be increased significantly, including attendance at fairs and events and including the final event.

However, the project will foreseeably suffer an extension of deadlines due to the unavoidable delays produced in the technical part by the pandemic. The communication of the project has been monitoring the evolution of the project, as well as the internal consortium meetings and the presentation of the project and the different Circular Cases in relevant sectoral events throughout Europe.

The project's dissemination activities have also been delayed due to the pandemic, for several reasons. On the one hand, the internal sharing of results and progress has had to be replaced by telematic meetings, which reduces the efficiency of internal communication and thus the public exposure of the results. On the other hand, there have been unavoidable delays in the technical developments of the project, leading to a delay in the presentation and presentation of results.

And last but not least, the presentation and dissemination of the results of the project and of the different demonstrators is usually made in relevant sectoral events where the different professionals involved in the project meet each other, such as the scientific community, the construction and geotechnical sector, roads, waste, paper manufacturers, etc. The second part of the project was very active and prolific in the face-to-face dissemination of results at events, congresses and fairs, projecting a very promising future that was drastically interrupted by COVID.

Today, efforts in dissemination of results have been redoubled due to the change of strategy and medium. Today, virtual meetings, webinars and workshops have meant a change in the working paradigm. Everyone has become accustomed to working and attending conferences, events, specialised webinars and accessible online.

The accessibility of the delivery of results has therefore improved dramatically, but it is increasingly difficult to find and retain the most relevant stakeholders. In a face-to-face event, we have "captive" conference attendees who want to attend a project presentation, but in this new paradigm, it is necessary to develop new and fresh content that can capture and retain the attention of potential end-users, policy makers and other key stakeholders for replicability and exploitation.

For this reason, it has been decided to work on the development of new communication materials for the project, such as video animations of each of the Circular Cases. Likewise, work is being carried out on the dissemination of the results, through the adaptation of contents and formats to digital media in the coming months.

Finally, most of the technical publications, specialized articles and peer reviewed articles follow the same curve as the project and will be developed in the last quarter of the project and will be presented in the final version of the Data Management Plan.

This report is developed in several distinct blocks that present the results framed in the different periodic reports. Throughout the project, the progress of all tasks, including C&D activities, has been evaluated through 3 reporting periods:

- The first periodic report covered the months M1 to M18, where the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D9.1), the Data Management Plan (D9.2) and most of the Communication Materials (D9.3), including their implementation strategy, were elaborated. The Circular Case started to be developed and mainly communication work on the progress of the project was developed, expanding the communication materials made available for C&D activities. This was due to the huge amount of information and developments covered by the project.

- The second periodic report covered 18 months, from M19 to M36, and ended in May 2020. During this period, the results obtained in the first Circular Case developed began to be obtained and presented, which led to a significant increase in the presence of the consortium partners at events, congresses and exhibitions. All the new communication

materials made available were used and have served (and are serving) to present the project quickly. The end of this period saw a halt in face-to-face dissemination activities due to the COVID pandemic, which led to a subsequent rethink of the dissemination and communication strategy.

- The third and last reporting period corresponds to the months M37 to M48, with an extension of the project foreseeable due to the pandemic and not confirmed at the date of submission of this report. During this period, most of the attendance at events for the presentation of results was planned, including a series of workshops in the countries where the Circular Cases have been developed. Due to the pandemic, the entire strategy has migrated to digital environments and it has been decided to expand the digital communication materials in order to capture, present and introduce the project prior to the dissemination activities.

1.2 Communication & Dissemination Objectives

According to the D9.1 Communication & Dissemination Plan, the main objective of WP9 is to secure the successful dissemination and communication activities towards public in general and potentially interested parties, positioning for future market replication and the commercial exploitation of the project's results. This main objective can be broken down into:

Objective 1 - To promote and encourage new approaches developed by the PAPERCHAIN cluster to relevant stakeholders identified to apply these new technical solutions for their own activities or infrastructures, in order to replicate them in a future.

Objective 2 - To promote and create new circular economy business models into large Pulp and Paper Industries and their value chain, to create value from wastes in a sustainable way.

Objective 3 - To transfer knowledge about new raw materials to decrease environmental impacts and increase socio-economical ones.

1.3 Target stakeholders and audiences

Initially they were identified the following industries:

- **Pulp & Paper Industries (PPIs) and associations**
- **Circular economy experts and associations**
- **Waste management companies and associations**
- **Logistic companies and associations**
- **Construction companies and associations**
- **Chemical companies and associations**
- **Mining companies and associations**
- **Others intermediaries or sectors, such as Landscape professionals**

For more information on target groups and identified stakeholders, please refer to D9.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan.

1.4 Main challenges

The main identified challenges are summarized in the following table. The dissemination of the results must include these topics as well as being aligned with the exploitation and replicability plan.

Type of Challenge	Complementary Challenge and Description
Societal	Contributing towards resource efficiency and raw materials, climate action and environment.
	To transfer knowledge (internally and externally) about new raw materials to decrease environmental impacts and increase socio-economical ones
Scientific and Technological	To design the baseline for the CE models surrounding Pulp and paper Industry
	To design the circular model schemes for Industrial Symbiosis
	To implement the valorisation processes at Industrial-scale
	To demonstrate the circular model at real-scale.
	To validate the sustainability of Circular economy model
	To carry out the certification processes, training and guidelines for the recycled solutions.
Industrial	Paperchain focus on one of the main challenges the Pulp and Paper industry is facing, which is waste streams that goes to landfill (currently).
	Paperchain project brings in an industrial symbiosis model centred in the use of different waste streams generated by a resource intensive Pulp and Paper sector, as a valuable feedstock for the three-resource consuming industrial sectors, mining, construction and chemical.
	The pulp industry is an important emitter of greenhouse gasses, even though, these are mainly from biogenic origin. The European pulp industry is well organized but remains under pressure from Asian competition. The production of second-generation biofuels via gasification and Fisher-Tropsch synthesis produces high quality biofuels, but is economically unviable from wood alone.
	The pulp industry has access to “high quality”, cheap and especially homogeneous feedstocks. The production of biofuels as part of the pulp cycle could addresses both challenges of the pulp industry and increase the competitive position of the pulp mills.

2-Communication Materials

The following lines describe all the communication materials developed for the project to date and when they were developed. It also describes those that are being developed to be used in the last stage of the project.

The following communication materials complements D9.2 Communication Materials, developed on the 8th month of the project. Because each of the demonstrators was totally different from the others, case-specific communication materials were developed to ensure that they had a wider and better dissemination impact.

All the communication materials have been designed by Greenize Projects, the leading partner of the communication and dissemination WP.

All the materials have been developed in English and eventually translated into other languages, aiming to target regional and national key stakeholders.

2.1-Logo, templates and visual identity

In month 8 of the project deliverable D9.2 Communication Materials was presented with the project logo, templates and the basis of the visual identity of all communication materials that have been developed throughout the project.

The project's website and intranet were also developed and have served as the main channel for the project's communication and dissemination activities, both internally and externally.

FIGURE 1 PAPERCHAIN LOGO

2.1-C&D Materials

Each of the Circular Cases has a leaflet and an exclusive explanatory rollup in English. In the case of CC2, developed in Spain, these materials are in Spanish and English by specific requirement of the partners involved in. Both, the leaflet and the rollup of each of the Circular Cases, include an infographic describing the circular diagram of the case.

In addition, a rollup and a generic trifold was designed, with a general explanation of the project and each of the Circular Cases that make it up.

Both leaflets and rollups were printed and distributed at trade fairs, congresses and conferences exclusively up to the M36. From the M36 onwards, these communication

FIGURE 3-CC2 CIRCULAR DIAGRAM

FIGURE 4-CC3 CIRCULAR DIAGRAM

FIGURE 4-CC4 CIRCULAR DIAGRAM

FIGURE 5 -CC5 CIRCULAR DIAGRAM

2.1.2-Leaflets and trifold

Leaflets consist in a double sheet of papers printed in both sides and folded. The purpose of this pamphlet is to serve as a flyer and is intended to be used for wide distribution and a quick introduction of the project during events or meetings.

A summary with the main figures of the project was designed in a trifold format, in order to distinguish from Demo Cases, giving a general perspective of the project.

The list of infographics designed in the M1-M18 period is as follows:

- **Trifold with main figures of the project.**
- **4 pages Leaflets for Demo Case 1 (English version)**
- **4 pages Leaflets for Demo Case 2 (English version)**
- **4 pages Leaflets for Demo Case 2 (Spanish version)**
- **4 pages Leaflets for Demo Case 3 (English version)**

The list of infographics designed in the M19-M36 period is as follows:

- **4 pages Leaflets for Demo Case 4 (English version)**
- **4 pages Leaflets for Demo Case 5 (English version)**

For the last period of the project, M37-M48 it is expected to design a final leaflet.

FIGURE 5-LEAFLETS

Circular Case 1

Construction sector // Central Portugal
Valorisation of Paper industry's causticizing residuals (i.e. lime mud, slaker grits and green liquor dregs) as secondary raw materials for concrete and asphalt manufacturing.
Lime mud as concrete filler; slaker grits and DREGS as aggregates for asphalt pavements.

Circular Case 2

Construction sector // Northern Spain
Valorisation of ash produced in the energy recovery from paper waste produced by Recycling Pulp mills as alternative binder for soil stabilization works in road construction projects.
WPA and WPBA as alternative hydraulic road binders.

Circular Case 3

Construction sector // Slovenia
Valorisation of deinking paper sludge and waste paper ash produced by Recycling Pulp mills for rehabilitation and slope stabilization of landslides near Railway tracks.
DPA + DPS composite for railway applications (landslide stabilisation).

Circular Case 4

Chemical sector // Central Sweden
Valorisation of fibre sludge waste generated by the Pulp industry as secondary raw materials for the production of ethanol derivatives for the Chemical Industry (i.e. Paints).
Fibre sludge for advanced chemicals based on bioethanol.

Circular Case 5

Mining sector // Northern Sweden
Valorisation of green liquor dregs produced by the Pulp industry as reactive sealing layers for acid rock drainage mitigation in mine waste deposits.
DREGS as sealing layer for mining spoil.

WHO WE ARE

A team of experts from academia, public authorities, waste generators, and industrial end-users, with additional support from other key stakeholders to cover the entire value-chain of a Circular Economy model.

CONNECT WITH US

We want to hear from you

info@paperchain.eu
 @paperChain_pro
 @the-paperchain-project
 @paperchain_pro

paperChain
www.paperchain.eu

For dissemination activities you can reach:
info@greenize.es

COORDINATOR

PARTNERS

THIRD & SUPPORTING PARTIES

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Version 2 - 2019-02

FIGURE 6-TRIFOLD

FROM WASTE TO RAW MATERIAL

dregs, grits and lime mud

Wastes

Why are they so good for construction materials?

Dregs

- ▶ Composed essentially by calcium, magnesium and iron compounds (including about 70%)
- ▶ They are dug and using the particle size is sorted to the optimal filter, or fine aggregate used
- ▶ Only marginal amounts of heavy metals, being concentrated near heavy metals

GRITS

- ▶ Around 90% of limestone
- ▶ After drying and making the particle size is sorted to the fine aggregate of their useful sand
- ▶ Only marginal amounts of heavy metals, being concentrated near heavy metals

Lime Mud

- ▶ Around 90% of limestone
- ▶ Particle size distribution with 90% below 0.3 µm

WHO WE ARE

A team of experts from academia, public authorities, waste generators, and industrial end-users, with additional support from other key stakeholders to cover the entire value-chain of a Circular Economy model.

PARTNERS INVOLVED

MEGAVIA: Construction SME responsible for execution of asphalt pavements. Modifications at the manufacturing plant to use dregs and grits as secondary raw material. Execution of road stretch.

The Navigator Company (NVG): Pulp and Paper Company generating the waste, responsible for management of waste handling, selection and processing to improve the quality of dregs, grits and lime mud.

SPRAL: Concrete products manufacturing SME. Execution of required modifications at the concrete manufacture plant to use Lime mud as secondary raw material. Execution of field trial.

University of Aveiro (UAVER): R&D partner responsible for the demo coordination and technical support for calculation, modelling, materials and solutions characterisation and testing.

CENTRO HABITAT: The Habitat Cluster is a competitiveness cluster representing the construction value chain, and is particularly involved in the specific role of dissemination of the project activities at national level and throughout its European contacts, as well as in the involvement of potential stakeholders (market queries, capacity, workshops) in the project actions. The Sustainable Habitat Cluster brings together companies, municipalities, R&D centers, business associations and other entities that are committed to sustainability as a motto for Innovation and Competitiveness.

RAIZ: Forest and Paper Research Institute from NVG. Responsible for providing support on the physical and chemical characterisation, of the industrial by-products coming from NVG, and in the analysis of environmental performance of the products through its life cycle.

STAKEHOLDERS OF THE DEMO CASE

Partners

Third And Supporting Parties

FIGURE 7-CC1 LEAFLET

FROM WASTE TO RAW MATERIAL

Case Study 2 of the Paperchain project uses the ashes from paper waste energy recovery (WPA) as a new hydraulic road binder, replacing lime and cement and avoiding landfill.

Waste Paper Ash (WPA)
Why are they an excellent hydraulic road binder?

Particle size: 30 µm
High fines: 4000 mg/kg
C2S: C3A
Free Lime
High fire time

WHO WE ARE

A team of experts from academia, public authorities, waste generators, and industrial end-users, with additional support from other key stakeholders to cover the entire value-chain of a Circular-Economy model.

Partners Involved

ACCIONA: Field trial design and execution. General demonstration activity coordination.

UPC: University providing technical support for dimensioning, structural calculation, modelling, testing and monitoring.

TECNALIA: Environmental impact assessment and environmental monitoring.

Supporting parties:

Pulp and paper industry:
SAICA which will provide the required waste amounts for the demos.

Public Authorities:
Municipalities of **El Burgo de Ebro, Villamayor de Gállego** and **Ejea de los Caballeros**, **Regional Government of Aragón** supporting the demonstration activities and potential adopters of the circular models.

STAKEHOLDERS OF THE DEMO CASE

FIGURE 8-CC2 LEAFLET

FROM WASTE TO RAW MATERIAL

Case Study 3 uses the ash coming from the energy recovery of paper waste combined with the sludge generated in the deinking process of the recycled fibres. The combination constitutes as a new backfill which replaces gravel material avoiding landfilling.

Wastes (DPA, DPS and Mudpel)
Why are they so good for landslide stabilisation?

Drinking paper ash (DPA, DPA)

- Particle size distribution with 50% below 15 µm
- Accumulated carbon carbamate
- Accumulated sulfur

Drinking paper sludge (DPS)

- Carbonaceous which makes it a main part of the raw material
- Residual sludge which should be sent to the construction site

New composite MUDPEL

- Low water
- High shear strength resistant
- High uniaxial compressive strength
- Low permeability
- Avoids small deformations

WHO WE ARE

A team of experts from academia, public authorities, waste generators, and industrial end-users, with additional support from other key stakeholders to cover the entire value-chain of a Circular-Economy model.

Partners Involved

Duran Huelak (DH): Construction SME in charge of implementing the developed solution on the demonstration site. DH will perform earthwork with machinery prepared to the site. The company is responsible for the geomechanical reports, including borehole drilling to get geotechnical model of the landslide. The project design of the retaining wall will be based on the geomechanical measurements, laboratory tests and the results of the uniaxial stability analysis. The project will include all the details about the implementation of the composite MUDPEL into the landslide support system. DH will blend the materials to prepare the MUDPEL, and transport it to the construction site.

VIPAP: Pulp and paper mill generating the waste. They will improve the handling for both materials, optimizing the process in order to improve waste quality. VIPAP will provide all the data about the waste production, quality assurance and realizable quick testing of the material during the mixing phase. Finally, VIPAP provides all data analysis needed for the design of a novel circular economy model based on this experience.

ZAG: Research Institute is in charge of the design of the innovative composite (DPA/DPS) MUDPEL in a defined ratio. Characterization and testing at laboratory level for the demonstration activity. ZAG will prepare the plan for the geomechanical characterization of the landslide and will provide all in situ and laboratory geomechanical tests for the landslide stability analysis. ZAG will provide technical support in order to achieve the required quality of the composite for this purpose, different mixtures of the composite will be tested according to the required mechanical and environmental standards. ZAG laboratories have accreditation according to the standard ISO 9001:2015. As a monitoring authority ZAG will grant Slovenian Technical Approvals (STO) for MUDPEL, based on the results of the mechanical and environmental tests. ZAG will also carry out the quality control of the MUDPEL, and the rest of the tests to check the compliance of the technical requirements of the construction project. Finally, ZAG will be in charge of the environmental and geomechanical monitoring.

S2 Infrastructure (S2): S2 Infrastructure is a Slovenian Railways Infrastructure Operator and End User. S2 will select an appropriate site with identified landslide problem. The security during the construction work will be organized by S2 service and as well as the technical support for the Circular Case 3. S2 will provide all necessary data about the existing materials and construction procedures. For the economic model and the design of a novel circular economy model S2 will collect all necessary information.

TECNALIA: Environmental impact assessment and environmental monitoring support.

STAKEHOLDERS OF THE DEMO CASE

FIGURE 9-CC3 LEAFLET

FIGURE 10-CC4 LEAFLET

FIGURE 11-CC5 LEAFLET

2.1.3- Posters & Rollups

A new version of the rollups was designed for each of the Circular Cases, also including a generic rollup where the 5 cases are exposed.

All the new rollup designs were printed and distributed among the leaders of each Circular Case, so that they can be used frequently in conferences, congresses and sectorial fairs. In addition, leaflets were sent to each leader of the different Circular Cases to be distributed whenever there is an opportunity.

The list of rollups and posters designed in the M1-M18 period is as follows:

- ✓ **Poster for IMWA Congress, Finland 2017.**
- ✓ **Rollup for Demo Case 1 (Designed for Techdays 2018 Exhibition in Portugal)**
- ✓ **Rollup for Demo Case 2 (Exposed in Innovacarreteras 2017 in Spain)**
- ✓ **Poster for CONAMA 2018 (Exposed in Conama 2018 in Spain)**

✓ **Poster for ECOMONDO 2018 (Exposed in Ecomondo 2018 in San Marino)**

The list of rollups and posters designed in the M19-M36 period is as follows:

- **Poster for World Road Congress, Abu Dhabi 2019.**
- **Rollup for Circular Case 1**
- **Rollup for Circular Case 2**
- **Rollup for Circular Case 3**
- **Rollup for Circular Case 4**
- **Rollup for Circular Case 5**
- **Rollup generic for all Circular Cases**

For the last period of the project, M37-M48 it is not expected to design more rollups nor posters.

FIGURE 12 ROLLUP & LEAFLETS IN ECOMONDO EXHIBITION

FIGURE 13 - ROLLUPS DESIGN FOR THE PROJECT

2.1.4- Video and Photos

During the project, the videos about the implementation of the Circular Cases have been included in the YouTube Channel of the project (The paperChain Team), on this link:

[YouTube - The paperChain Team](#)

Some partners such as ACCIONA and Boliden have published their own video about the execution of their demo cases.

It was expected to create a final video, however and due to pandemic, the new C&D strategy is focusing on improving digital communication materials and as result five video animations are being created to promote the project and involve wider audiences. These video animation videos will be publicly published in February or March 2021, in order to get them ready for webinars, workshops and other virtual events.

2.1.5- Others

Additional graphic materials that support communication and dissemination activities were produced during 2018.

- ✓ **vCard or presentation card for generic purpose (All members).**
- ✓ **Vcard or presentation card for personal use (Project manager).**
- ✓ **Two big promotional banners**

FIGURE 14-ADDITIONAL GRAPHIC MATERIALS

3-C&D Channels

3.1- Webpage

The main domain, www.paperchain.eu is the core of all the communication and dissemination materials, a place to manage and share all the updated information about the project, activities and results. During this project, the communication of the advances has relied more on social networks than on the use of newsletters linked to emailing.

The webpage was launched in English in 2017 and designed and managed by Greenize Projects, containing the following sections:

- **Home**
- **The project**
- **Circular Cases**
- **Consortium**
- **Contact**
- **Publications**
- **Press**
- **News**

All the news are published on the webpage, as well as in social media, having a complete repository of the events attended by paperChain. Publications, press releases, photos and videos and more info about the project and the Circular Cases are available on the webpage.

FIGURE 15-LANDING PAGE

INNOVACARRETERA 2019

EVENTS, NEWS
22
November.
2019

During the 29th, 30th and 31st of October, the two most important events in the Road sector in Spain were held jointly: the **30th Road Week** (organised by the Spanish Road Association) and **Innovacarretera 2019** (organised by the PTC – Road Technology Platform). This year, the event was held at the Palacio de Congresos in Santiago de Compostela and had 174 registrations for the event.

FIGURE 16 NEWS ON WEBPAGE

3.2-Social Networks

PAPERCHAIN project uses these main social networks:

Twitter ([@paperChain_pro](https://twitter.com/paperChain_pro))

LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company-beta/11203976/>)

Instagram (https://www.instagram.com/paperchain_pro/)

YouTube (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCU3LiP_OvMopn0fYZ99SEDQ)

Communications via social networks will focus on the general advance of the demo cases, as well as disseminating contents and results for wider audiences.

FIGURE 17 TWITTER POST

FIGURE 18 INSTAGRAM POST

FIGURE 19 LINKEDIN POST

3.3-Press Releases

Along the project, a press release has been launched each time a Circular Case has completed its implementation on site. In addition, some other press release has been launched with other relevant events, such as the one concerning to the Award won in the World Road Congress in Abu Dhabi, October 2019.

The press releases are posted on the project's website, through a kit for quick download and being linked from the different social media channels.

3.4-Impact on Media

Along the project, Greenize has coordinated the dissemination and communication activities, stepping on the communication departments of all partners involved in the consortium. In this way, real impacts will not correspond only to the visits to the paperChain webpage but reaching wider audiences through newsletter from all partners. For these reasons, e-newsletters were not a key channel for the paperChain project.

Media appearances increased whenever they echoed the implementation of the Circular Cases and for other events, as the award received by PIARC in Abu Dhabi. An increase of visits in every social media profile was detected after the release of the press release.

Every Circular Case leader is responsible for collecting a national online clipping after any relevant press release or publication.

Some media appearance during the CC2 in Spain is as follows:

Construible.es

<https://www.construible.es/2018/10/01/provincia-zaragoza-acogera-primer-prueba-proyecto-europeo-paperchain-economia-circular>

Newsletter Construible: <https://us10.campaign-archive.com/?e=32b0556ab8&u=13772b4410c1c16fd2e367650&id=4b2e97315b>

Retema.es

<https://www.retema.es/noticia/el-proyecto-de-economia-circular-paperchain-realizara-en-zaragoza-su-primer-caso-prac-DjyIn>

FuturEnviro,es

Newsletter FuturEnviro:

http://r.saguenay.inkamkt.com/mk/mr/ebVrFwiscpq4U8xpP9kPvSlCQS1bgf7E6l-EhEILWdU2SesHv5SNq_qayR- N8RKXqtiQOQ6Z73enu_53G_pGN72XTEC9IBZ8RfOQvdrfgLx

<https://futurenviro.es/paperchain-realizara-en-zaragoza-su-primer-caso-practico/>

Residuosprofesional.com

<https://www.residuosprofesional.com/paperchain-residuos-industria-papelera/>

circpack.eu

<https://mailchi.mp/circpack.eu/circ-pack-newsletter-october-2018?e=72d9aee3db>

Local media and television

https://youtu.be/bjnog5_07ls

<http://aragonhoy.aragon.es/index.php/mod.noticias/mem.detalle/id.230364>

<http://aragonhoy.aragon.es/index.php/mod.noticias/mem.detalle/id.230208>

<https://mailchi.mp/circpack.eu/circ-pack-newsletter-october-2018?e=72d9aee3db>

Social media

LinkedIn Acciona ES:

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6452815623108993024/>

LinkedIn Acciona EN:

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6452822661415337984/>

An increase of visits in every social media profile was detected after the release of the press release.

FIGURE 20 LINKEDIN-PRESS-RELEASE

3.1.7 Communication by the partners

Within the members of the project, it has also been disseminated through the communication channels, social media, e-newsletters and websites of the partners of the consortium.

PARTNER	LINK
ACCIONA	https://www.accionaconstruccion.com/es/innovacion/proyectos-de-innovacion/materiales/paperchain/
	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4_hWXuiQSNQ
	https://www.accionaconstruccion.com/es/salaprensa/noticias/2019/octubre/cenizas-valorizacion-energetica-residuo-papel-alternativa-sostenible-cemento-cal-estabilizacion-carreteras/
UPC	https://cit.upc.edu/es/destacados/proyecto_paperchain_economia_circular_transformar_residuos_de_papel_en_materias_primas_secundaria
	https://upcommons.upc.edu/handle/2117/188107
	https://www.recercat.cat/handle/2072/363775
CENTRO HABITAT	http://www.centrohabitat.net/en/proyecto/paperchain
LGI	http://lgi-consulting.com/paperchain-h2020-wins-prize-for-best-innovation/
MEGAVIA	http://megavia.pt/?page_id=182

TABLE 1-COMMUNICATIONS OF THE PROJECT THROUGH PARTNERS' WEBSITES

4-Events

Partners have to identify yearly more relevant events, congresses, conferences and exhibitions concern to their own sector. Main topics are circular economy, pulp and paper, construction, mining, chemical and others.

The objective is to spread out the ongoing progress and results of paperChain to potential audiences and key stakeholders. This must be done in a national, European and global level. Every time a partner has attended an event, a social media post and a new on the website were created.

As advanced in the Executive Summary and Introduction of this report, the main efforts to attend and disseminate results of paperChain were expected for the last quarter of the project. During most part of 2020, all the events were postponed due to the reality of COVID 19, so the planning and expectations of presenting the project in relevant congresses, conferences and fairs have been adapted to this situation, transforming face-to-face events into virtual ones. This means not only a change of format, but a global change of format, content and dissemination strategy. In addition, 5 national workshops will be held in the coming months until the end of the project.

During the next months, until the end of the project, most of the research and conclusions from the implementation of the demonstrators, as well as data from the monitoring of the Circular Cases will be generated.

The dissemination of the publications generated will be done according to the Data Management Plan, described in deliverable D9.2 of the project. These publications will be accompanied by a series of technical webinars, due to the restrictions of mobility and the development of face-to-face events.

3.2.1-Congresses, Exhibitions, Conferences, Events Attended by Consortium

Project partners have actively participated in relevant events, conferences and congresses exposing the paperChain project. The complete list of attended events is as follows:

TABLE 2-LIST OF EVENTS ATTENDED BY CONSORTIUM

#	YEAR	PERIODIC REPORT	STARTING DATE	ENDING DATE	ATTENDING PARTNERS	EVENT NAME	CITY	COUNTRY	TOPIC (s)
1	2017	1	2017-11-03		GREENIZE	Circular Valladolid Weekend	Valladolid	SPAIN	Circular Economy
2	2017	1	2017-11-07		ACCIONA, GREENIZE	Plataforma Tecnológica de la Carretera	Madrid	SPAIN	Roads
3	2018	1	2018-06-06	2018-06-08	LTU	Wascon		FINLAND	Waste, Construction

4	2018	1	2018-10-11		UA, NAVIGATOR, RAIZ	Tech Days	Aveiro	PORTUGAL	
5	2018	1	2018-10-16	2018-10-17	LGI	Paper & Beyond (CEPI)	Brussels	BELGIUM	PPI
6	2018	1	2018-10-22	2018-10-24	ACCIONA	WCEF 2018	Tokyo	JAPAN	Circular Economy
7	2018	1	2018-11-06	2018-11-09	ACCIONA, GREENIZE	ECOMONDO	Rimini	SAN MARINO	Sustainability, Circular Economy
8	2018	1	2018-11-26	2018-11-29	ACCIONA, GREENIZE	CONAMA	Madrid	SPAIN	Sustainability, Circular Economy
9	2019	2	2019-02-24	2019-02-27	ACCIONA, ZAG	WORLD RESOURCES FORUM	Antwerp	BELGIUM	Sustainability, Circular Economy
10	2019	2	2019-05-23		TECNALIA	UBU - Presentacion	Burgos	SPAIN	Sustainability, Circular Economy
11	2019	2	2019-06-03	2019-06-05	ACCIONA	WCEF 2019	Helsinki	FINLAND	Sustainability, Circular Economy
			2019-07-03		ACCIONA	Green Transformation Program- Partner workshop	Madrid	SPAIN	Circular economy, PPI waste, Construction, Cement substitute, Secondary raw material
12	2019	2	2019-10-6	2019-10-10	ACCIONA, UPC	XXVI th World Road Congress	Abu Dhabi	ABU DHABI	Roads
13	2019	2	2019-10-7	2019-10-9	TECNALIA, LGI	ISWA	Bilbao	SPAIN	Waste
14	2019	2	2019-10-15	2019-10-18	UPC, GAIKER, GREENIZE	19th ERSCP	Barcelona	SPAIN	Sustainability, Circular Economy
15	2019	2	2019-10-30		TECNALIA, ACCIONA, GREENIZE	INNOVACARRETERAS	Santiago de Compostela	SPAIN	Roads
16	2020	3	2020-10-19	2020-10-21	LTU	E-UNSAT2020 - Unsaturated Horizons 4TH EUROPEAN CONFERENCE ON UNSATURATED SOILS	Online (expected in Lisbon)	PORTUGAL	Geology, mining
17	2020	3	2020-10-30		ACCIONA	ECONOMÍA CIRCULAR CONSTRUCCION SOSTENIBLE	Online (expected in Logroño and hosted by Universidad de La Rioja)	SPAIN	Construction, Circular Economy

In addition to this list, an application was made to participate in the following event, which was finally rejected, so the project could not be represented:

- **2019_09_24-24-26-European Research and Innovation Days 2019 – Brussels (Belgium)**

One of the most outstanding events in which the consortium has participated was the recognition of a paper presented by the project as the best innovation Award at the World Road Congress, organized by PIARC and held in Abu Dhabi in October 2019.

Paper: ["Alternative Secondary Raw Materials for Road Construction Based on Pulp and Paper Industry Reject"](#), presented by members of ACCIONA, TECNALIA and UPC.

FIGURE 21-BEST INNOVATION AWARD

RAIZ, as third party involved in paperChain project, has participated in several congresses, listed as follows:

- ✓ **European Workshop on Lignocellulosics and Pulp – Aveiro (29th June 2018)**

Title: Pulp Industry Wastes as Raw Materials: a Circular Economy Approach

Speaker: Susana Pereira

- ✓ **XXIV International Forest, Pulp and Paper Conference - Aveiro (Tecnicepa – Outubro 2018)**

Title: A Circular Economy Approach: Pulp Industry Wastes as Raw Materials

Speaker: Susana Pereira

- ✓ **Workshop Biorrefinaria na Industria de Pasta e Papel: novos produtos e aplicações – Aveiro (RAIZ – 23rd November 2018)**

Title: Resíduos da Indústria de Pasta e Papel como Matérias-primas: Economia Circular

Speaker: Susana Pereira

✓ **Workshop Technologic Transfer – Dynamics for Innovation (Ciclo de Eventos ANI) – Oliveira do Hospital (BLC3 – 20th November 2019)**

Title: Integração de resíduos em materiais de construção e aditivos de remediação de solos

Speaker: Nazaré Almeida

✓ **Agrovouga'19 – Fair – Aveiro (Aveiro City Hall – 20-24th November 2019)**

Agrovouga is an annual fair organized by Aveiro City hall and focus on promotion of local (Aveiro region) agribusiness trends in the fields of innovation, environmentally friendly technologies, renewable energies, forest research and management, the valorisation of local products and ecosystem services, new forms of consumption, organic products and sustainability.

In 2019 edition, RAIZ guaranteed its participation by setting up a stand to display the research work developed at the institute at the forest level and new market products focused on sustainability. The dissemination of the project paperChain was done by displaying a poster and also the laboratorial samples of pre-cast concrete and bituminous mixture, as well with distribution of the project flyers.

✓ **MySustainableForest 3rd Workshop – Aveiro (RAIZ – 28th January 2020)**

The biorrefinery research group, from RAIZ, guaranteed its participation on the event by setting up a stand during the workshop, to display the research work developed at the institute and focused on circular economy.

The dissemination of the project paperChain was done by displaying a poster and also the laboratorial samples of pre-cast concrete and bituminous mixture, as well with distribution of the project flyers.

✓ **XXV International Forest, Pulp and Paper Conference – Virtual Conference (Tecnicepa – March 2021) (accepted for poster presentation)**

Title: Implementation of two Circular Economy demonstration cases in Portugal: Challenges and Learnings

Speaker: Nazaré Almeida

3.2.1-Workshops held by paperChain's Consortium

Taking advantage of the opportunity that during the General Assembly all the partners of the project met, two workshops have been developed to expose the project to key entities and stakeholders. They were held in the second periodic report, from M18 to M36:

- **2019, the 12th of June – Lulea Technical University, Sweden**
- **2019, the 14th of November – University of Aveiro, Portugal**

Five additional workshops are planned, in accordance with the initial objectives of the project, which will be developed by each of the leaders of each Circular Case, possibly virtually.

In parallel, paperChain project has been invited by EASME to participate in a European workshop, under the title "Innovative methods to remove hazardous substances and contaminants from secondary raw materials for the circular economy", to be held at the end of February, digitally.

It is possible that in the coming months there will be other interesting initiatives where the results and achievements of the project can be presented through different workshops and round tables.

AGENDA. 1st draft at 25th of September

Wednesday 13.11.2019	
9.00 – 9.15	Welcome session. University of Aveiro. General information and practical tips. Logistics of the GA.
9.15 – 9.30	ACCIONA. Project update. Project progress, pending amendment, main outcomes, remarks from the coordinator.
9.30 – 10:30	Status of the demonstration activities (CC1 to CC5). General information about the progress. Technical details in the evening.
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee Break
11:00 – 11:45	WP6. LCCSA. Last outcomes and demands
11:45 – 12:30	WP7. Certification and market uptake. Presentation and open discussion
12:30 – 13:00	WP8. Exploitation. Preliminary results of task 8.2 & open discussion
13.00 – 14.00	Lunch
Workshop "Paperchain circular cases – Industrial symbiosis between Paper & Pulp industry and other industrial sectors"	
14.00 – 15.30	I. Presentation of Circular Cases CC1. Precast concrete and Road surface layer. 15 min. AVRO/NAVIGATOR/SPRAL/MEGAVIA CC2. Soil cement layer in A33 highway. 15 min. ACC CC3. Last works to finish the pilot. 15 min ZAG CC4. Description of works up to now. 15 min Processum/SEKAB/DOM CC5. Startling of demo activities. 15 min. LUT/BOL
15.30 – 16.00	II. Technical and environmental monitoring of pilot cases Aveiro Univ./ TECNALIA-UPC / ZAG / Processum / LUT-BOL. /open discussion A 5 min presentation of each partner about their monitoring and discussion on minimum content of common KPIs.
16.00 – 16.30	Coffee Break
16.30– 17.00	Tips for the next day & Closing session. AVRO & ACC
20:00	DINNER

TABLE 3-AGENDA OF THE GENERAL ASSEMBLY IN AVEIRO-PORTUGAL- INCLUDING WORKSHOP

FIGURE 22-PICTURE OF THE WORKSHOP IN AVEIRO

FIGURE 23-DETAIL ABOUT COMMUNICATION MATERIALS IN AVEIRO WORKSHOP

In Portugal, professionals from different companies attended the workshop.

<http://www.centrohabitat.net/en/evento/workshop-paperchain-circular-cases-industrial-symbiosis->

FIGURE 24-DETAIL ABOUT COMMUNICATION MATERIALS IN WORKSHOP IN LULEA -SWEDEN-

FIGURE 25-PICTURE OF THE WORKSHOP CELEBRATED IN LULEA -SWEDEN-

Wednesday 12.06.2019	
8.30 – 12.00	Presentations and discussion (administrative issues, intern information, etc) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction (JJCP, CM) to 9:00 h - Conclusions on WP4. V. Ferreira/M. Morais/H. Paiva to 9:30 h - Presentation of preliminary LCA. J. Ríos 10:00 -10.30 h - CE marking activities kick off. K. Fifer to 11:00 h - Demand assessment (Task 8.2). C. Auriault to 11:30 h - Update on Comm. & Diss. A. Cañas. To 12:00 h
12.00 – 13.00	Lunch
1300 – 15.30	Presentations of Demo 1-4 (together with GLAD-project, 20 min each) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presentation of Paperchain (JJCP) and GLAD-project (MB) - Demo 1. Presentation - Demo 2. Update on monitoring of pilots 1 & 2 and pilot 3 - Demo 3. Update on technical and environmental monitoring - Demo 4. Status and next movements.
16.00 – 19.00	Transportation to Malå
19.00	Diner

FIGURE 26-DETAIL OF GENERAL ASSEMBLY AGENDA, INCLUDING WORKSHOP, LULEA -SWEDEN-

Common seminar with the GLAD-project

One part of the GA will be done in cooperation with another research project, gathering most of the pulp mills in Sweden. GLAD is financed by a Swedish fund and is specifically working on the valorization of GLD for mitigation of mine waste deposits. The idea is to present Paperchain for them and vice versa. The people from GLAD will be invited to the afternoon presentations and the study visit.

FIGURE 27-CONTENT OF THE WORKSHOP

3.2.1-Collaboration with other H2020 funded projects

In 2019, February the 24th to 27th, paperChain partners from ACCIONA and ZAG were attending and presenting a side event of the World Resources Forum within the

collaboration of other H2020 funded project. The topic of this side-event was the Industrial Symbiosis, and it was prepared during several months in advance by Greenize, creating the following agenda and even own graphic materials:

Organized by:

The projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

Industrial Symbiosis in Europe.

SIDE-EVENT AGENDA

1st Day | 25th February Gorilla Room1

- 14:00 **Opening statement: Industrial Symbiosis in Europe and the vision of the process industries**
Angels Ostula - A SPIRE
- 14:15 **EPOS Toolbox**
Griet Van Eetvelde (UGent) & Ivan Kantor (EPFL) - EPOS Project
Introduction and explanation of the EPOS toolbox. Presentation of generic IS cases.
- 15:15 **New valuable applications from the Pulp & Paper Industry waste. Practical examples of Industrial Symbiosis**
Juan José Cepeda (ACCIONA) - PAPERCHAIN Project
Description of results from the collaboration among different sectors and the Pulp & Paper industry. How to gather requirements for the innovative valorisation of complex waste streams.
- MUDIPEL, an innovative composite material made of different paper**
Karmen Filiz (ZAG) - PAPERCHAIN Project
Practical example of the solutions developed in the project.
- 16:00 **Break** Projection of project videos in the conference room
- 16:15 **FISSAC Industrial Symbiosis Platform**
Davide Maglio (RINA) & Ozge Yimaz (KODDENG) - FISSAC Project
Presentation and demonstration of the Industrial Symbiosis Platform developed under FISSAC Project. The platform connects facilities, symbiosis experts, government representatives and consultants under one roof to successfully create symbiosis networks. Key Features: Flexible production and facility modelling, LCA, LCC, API-based analysis and maintenance.
- 17:00 **SPRING: enhancing the impact of Industrial Symbiosis projects in the SPIRE portfolio**
Amy Pease (British) & John Henderson (British) - SPRING Project
An overview of activities and learning from the SPRING project to enhance the impact of collaborative projects, including methods to address barriers to industrial exploitation and approaches to aid better decision making when considering industry improvement opportunities.
- 17:30 **Closing Slide - Event 1st day**

2nd Day | 26th February Gorilla Room1

- 10:00 **Opening 2nd day: Industrial Symbiosis in Europe**
Angels Ostula - A SPIRE
- 10:15 **Best practices and key enabling technologies & intermediaries for effective industrial symbiosis**
Marco Calvino (IS3) & Cliona Howle (Climate-KIC) - SCALER Project
Presentation of the findings from SCALER's reports on Best practices and key enabling technologies & intermediaries for effective industrial symbiosis.
- 11:00 **Industrial symbiosis in the Urbanec project**
Sarah Riich (OVAM) & Luigi Pugliese (BPP) - URBANEC Project
The results of industrial symbiosis in the Urbanec project. Case study: the added value of the use of the Finnish symbiosis platform for providers of new technologies.
- 12:00 **SHAREBOX - How to acquire symbiotic synergies successfully on the web**
Angele Rodolin (ECS) - SHAREBOX Project
Introduction to the SHAREBOX concept and showcasing how the online solution works
- 13:00 **Lunch break** Projection of project videos in the conference room
- 15:00 **MAESTRI T4IS (Toolbox 4 Industrial Symbiosis)**
Daniel Suemmel (USAM) & Marco Calvino (IS3) - MAESTRI Project
Short overview of MAESTRI and then a focus on the work developed concerning IS, namely the T4IS.
- 16:00 **Collaborative demand response by optimal production scheduling in an industrial cluster**
Andres Balboa (ITIA) & Juliana Camargo (VITO) - SYMBOPTIMA Project
Integrated Solution for managing energy demand response of a cluster of companies, enabling local flexibility by energy aware production scheduling.
- Symby-Net: a new tool for industrial symbiosis**
Carlo Bronzi, Simone Comagi (ITIA) - SYMBOPTIMA Project
A tool to manage and optimize LCA aspects of industrial symbiosis networks.
- 17:30 **Closing Slide - Event 2nd day**

25th & 26th February Activities Booth28

- Showing of Industrial Symbiosis IT tools and live testing:
SHAREBOX online platform
EPOS IT toolbox
SYMBOPTIMA IT tools
The Finnish Symbiosis Platform (URBANEC)
FISSAC Industrial Symbiosis platform
- Exposition of samples - from initial waste to the valorized new materials
- Continuous projection of slides and presentations
- Meet & Great project partners
Project posters, banners and communication material

Currently, as a result of the Horizon Results Booster, work is being carried out on the dissemination of results with another European H2020 project, called Pulp & Fuel. The possibility of holding a joint workshop as part of the programme of another more relevant event is being studied.

3.2.1-Webinars

During 2021, a series of webinars on different topics is being planned, due to the change of strategy and the migration to virtual spaces. It is possible that the planned workshops will be used to host an informative session through the webinar format.

At the date of submission of this report, the content of the webinars is still being developed, trying to align them with the results of the exploitation and replicability plan, in order to maximise their impact among key agents. At the same time, efforts are being made to find sectoral events that can host these seminars. They will try to be hosted within other sectoral events, as the efforts to promote and attract relevant participants are enormous.

4-PUBLICATIONS

PAPERCHAIN's main outcomes and results will be published in Scientific Journals, relating developed technologies and demonstration cases in a technological-scientific way.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to involve partners from universities and research centres. Some of these articles will be shared in relevant Open Access Journals or Open Access Repositories, according to the initiative of H2020.

During M18 to M36 period, only some articles have been published in technical magazines, but no one peer reviewed.

4.1-Articles

The following articles have been published in technical magazines. All of them in Spain:

YEAR	MONTH	TITLE	MEDIA - JOURNAL - MAGAZINE	LANGUAGE	COUNTRY	TOPICS
2019	January	Proyecto paperChain: Nuevos modelos de economía circular para la industria papelera	FuturEnviro	EN + ES	Spain	Sustainability, circular economy
2019	March	Generacion de modelos de economía circular y uso de materiales de origen renovable para una construcción de firmas más sostenible	"Carreteras" by Asociación Española de la Carretera	EN + ES	Spain	Roads, circular economy
2019	December	Cenizas volantes de papelera aplicadas a la construcción de carreteras	PDF del nº 219 de RETEMA - Noviembre/Diciembre 2019	ES	Spain	Roads, circular economy, pulp and paper industry, sustainability

TABLE 4-LIST OF TECHNICAL ARTICLES PUBLISHED IN SECTORIAL MEDIA

artículo

Generación de modelos de economía circular y uso de materiales de origen renovable para una construcción de firmes más sostenible

Generation of circular economy models and use of renewable materials for a more sustainable pavements construction

Carlos MARTÍN-PORTUGUÉS MONTOLIU

Grupo de Carreteras y Medio Ambiente. Centro Tecnológico Acciona Construcción.
ACCIONA Construcción

Raquel CASADO BARRASA

Grupo de Carreteras y Medio Ambiente. Centro Tecnológico Acciona Construcción.
ACCIONA Construcción

Edith GUEDELLA BUSTAMANTE

Grupo de Carreteras y Medio Ambiente. Centro Tecnológico Acciona Construcción.
ACCIONA Construcción

RESUMEN

El aprovechamiento de residuos para la construcción y rehabilitación de carreteras es una estrategia a potenciar para establecer relaciones de simbiosis industrial de carácter regional que permita ganar competitividad a las empresas y reducir el impacto ambiental asociado a su actividad.

El presente artículo resume una serie de ejemplos específicos orientados, por un lado, a la generación de modelos de economía circular empleando residuos de la industria papelera para la estabilización de suelos, escorias de acería y arenas de fundición para la producción de mezclas asfálticas, o RCDs para la construcción de sub-bases granulares y, por otro, orientados a validar el uso de materiales de origen renovable para la construcción de capas de firmes (bio-polímeros como la lignina para la fabricación de betunes modificados con polímeros y agentes bio-rejuvenecedores para mejorar la trabajabilidad de las mezclas asfálticas y aumentar las tasas de material fresado o RAP).

PALABRAS CLAVE: Medioambiente, Reciclado, Firme sostenible, Economía circular, Residuo, Residuo de construcción y demolición RCD, Mezcla asfáltica, Estabilización.

ABSTRACT

The use of waste for the construction and rehabilitation of roads, is a strategy to be boosted to establish regional industrial symbiosis agreements that can support companies to gain competitiveness and reduce the environmental impact associated to their day to day business activity.

This article summarizes particular examples to generate on one hand circular economy models using waste from the pulp and paper industry for soil stabilization, steel slags and foundry sands for asphalt concrete manufacturing, C&DW for the construction of granular sub-bases and on the other to validate the use of renewable materials for pavements construction (bio-polymers like lignin for the production of polymer modified bitumen and bio-rejuvenator agents to enhance asphalt concrete workability and increase the use of reclaimed asphalt pavements or RAP).

KEY WORDS: Environment, Recycled, Sustainable pavement, Circular economy, Waste, Construction and demolition waste C&DW, Asphalt concrete, Stabilisation.

correteras

número 223 1

FIGURE 28- ARTICLE PUBLISHED IN ROADS MAGAZINE (2019)

CENIZAS VOLANTES DE PAPELERA APLICADAS A LA CONSTRUCCIÓN DE CARRETERAS. EXPERIENCIAS DEL PROYECTO PAPERCHAIN

Cenizas volantes de papelera aplicadas a la construcción de carreteras

Experiencias a gran escala del proyecto PaperChain

Juan José Ceprá, Roberto Orejana, Zaira de la Vega, Adriana Martínez, Rodrigo Miró, Marilda Barra, Diego Aponte, Hani Baloche, ACCIONA | www.accionacom.com • SAICA | www.saica.com • Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya | www.upc.edu

PAPERCHAIN BUSCA DAR SALIDA COMERCIAL A DIFERENTES RESIDUOS NO PELIGROSOS DE LA INDUSTRIA PAPELERA REDUCIENDO ASÍ LA TASA DE VERTIDO

El proyecto PaperChain "New Market Niches for the Pulp & Paper Industry Waste based on Circular Economy Approaches" reúne a 20 socios de 5 países europeos, así como a un gran número de colaboradores unidos con el objetivo común de encontrar nuevos nichos de mercado para diferentes residuos no peligrosos de la industria papelera que permitan reducir las tasas de envío a vertedero. Para ello,

partiendo de unas investigaciones previamente desarrolladas por el equipo de trabajo del proyecto, se busca demostrar a escala real y en entornos operativos la viabilidad del uso de estos residuos en tres sectores productivos con gran demanda de materias primas: construcción, minero y químico.

En concreto, en el caso de los trabajos llevados a cabo en España, el proyecto persigue reducir el impacto ambiental de la construcción de carreteras sustituyendo el cemento o la cal por cenizas provenientes del proceso de reciclaje de papel.

Aunque no se aprecie, las carreteras llevan importantes cantidades de cemento bajo el pavimento que se utilizan para mejorar las propiedades mecánicas de los suelos en las dife-

rentes capas que forman la sección estructural de las carreteras; son los denominados suelos estabilizados.

Los suelos estabilizados tienen una mayor capacidad soporte, un espesor reducido y por tanto, un menor consumo de materias primas. Además, permiten utilizar materiales procedentes de las excavaciones de la propia carretera que, sin estabilizar, por sus pobres propiedades mecánicas, irían destinados a vertedero.

Así entonces, el uso de conglomerantes hidráulicos contribuya por sí mismo al concepto de economía circular, dado que reduce impactos a lo largo de todo el ciclo de vida de la carretera. No obstante, no se puede olvidar que el cemento contribuye entre un 5 % (1) y un 8 % (2) al total de las emisiones mundiales de CO₂, en fun-

CENIZAS VOLANTES DE PAPELERA APLICADAS A LA CONSTRUCCIÓN DE CARRETERAS. EXPERIENCIAS DEL PROYECTO PAPERCHAIN

ción de la consideración del tipo de cemento producido. Poder sustituir el cemento por otros materiales que no contribuyan a las emisiones de CO₂ permitiría una reducción sustancial de la huella de carbono en la construc-

ción de carreteras y en concreto la utilización de las cenizas provenientes de la valorización energética de residuos papeleros permitiría además cerrar el círculo en el proceso de reciclaje de papel.

UN PROCESO COMPLETO DE RECICLADO

El uso de la ceniza como material para carreteras es tan solo el último paso del importante ciclo de Economía

Reducir el impacto ambiental de la construcción de carreteras sustituyendo el cemento o la cal por cenizas provenientes del proceso de reciclaje de papel, objetivo de las investigaciones de PaperChain

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FIGURE 29 - ARTICLE PUBLISHED IN 2019 - RETEMA MAGAZINE-

PROYECTO PAPERCHAIN: NUEVOS MODELOS DE ECONOMÍA CIRCULAR PARA LA INDUSTRIA PAPELERA

El Proyecto PaperChain, financiado por el Programa de Investigación y Desarrollo Horizonte 2020 de la Comisión Europea, propone la utilización de residuos generados en la industria papelera como materia prima secundaria para sectores intensivos en la utilización de recursos, como es el en el sector de la construcción, la minería y la industria química. Asimismo, contempla el desarrollo de soluciones innovadoras a través de cinco modelos comerciales de economía circular. El proyecto está conformado por 20 socios de cinco países (España, Portugal, Eslovenia, Francia y Suecia) y cuenta con un presupuesto de 7,8 M€.

La industria papelera europea produce anualmente unos 130 millones de toneladas de celulosa y papel, según datos de la Confederación Europea de Industrias del Papel (CEPI), una actividad que genera 11 millones de toneladas de residuos. Para dar salida a estas enormes cantidades de desechos, surge el proyecto europeo paperChain, cuyo principal objetivo es desarrollar cinco modelos de economía circular centrados en la valorización de los residuos procedentes de la industria papelera para utilizarlos, posteriormente, como materias primas secundarias en sectores industriales con un alto consumo de materias primas, como pueden ser el sector de la construcción, el minero o el químico.

Con un presupuesto de 7,8 M€, el proyecto está financiado por el Programa de Investigación y Desarrollo Horizonte 2020 de la Comisión Europea, siendo su principal objetivo promover la eficiencia en el consumo de recursos basándose en un modelo de simbiosis industrial, lo que vendrá a demostrar el gran potencial que tienen los principales residuos no peligrosos generados en la industria papelera (dregs, grits, lodos de destintado, cenizas volantes y lodos de planta de tratamiento primaria de aguas residuales) como fuente de materias primas secundarias. Así, el proyecto pretende demostrar el alto valor de estos residuos a través de tres formas diferentes: sin modificaciones, con un procesamiento mínimo y bajo cualquier tratamiento.

El consorcio paperChain está conformado por 20 socios de cinco países, esto es, Portugal, España, Eslovenia, Francia y Suecia, aglutinando toda la cadena de valor: desde el sector académico hasta las autoridades públicas, los generadores de residuos y los usuarios finales.

Para cada uno de los sectores estratégicos seleccionados se ha seguido un enfoque sistemático en el que se integra toda la cadena de valor, desde la generación del residuo hasta su aplicación final. En cada uno de los sectores se han incluido los diversos actores interesados de cada modelo de economía circular, incluyendo los generadores del residuo, los gestores, los usuarios finales y diversos entes sociales.

Los cinco modelos de economía circular propuestos son los siguientes:

En el sector de la construcción:

- *Modelo de economía circular 1:* Valoración de los residuos generados en los procesos alcalinos de producción de celulosa (dregs, grits y barro carbonatado) como áridos gruesos y finos en la producción de asfaltos y hormigón.
- *Modelo de economía circular 2:* Valorización de lodos de destintado de papel y cenizas volantes de valorización energética de residuos papeleros para la rehabilitación y estabilización de deslizamientos de ladera en líneas de ferrocarril.

PAPERCHAIN PROJECT: NEW CIRCULAR ECONOMY MODELS FOR THE PAPER INDUSTRY

The PaperChain project is funded by European Commission Horizon 2020 Research & Development Programme. It proposes the use of waste generated in the paper industry as secondary raw materials for resource-intensive sectors, such as construction, mining and the chemical industry. The project envisages the development of innovative solutions through five commercial circular economy models. The project consortium is made up of 20 partners from five countries (Spain, Portugal, Slovenia, France and Sweden) and the project has a budget of 7.8 million euro.

The European paper industry produces around 130 million tonnes of pulp and paper per annum, according to Confederation of European Paper Industry (CEPI) figures. This activity generates 11 million tonnes of waste. The European paperchain project seeks to provide an outlet for this large quantity of waste. The main objective of the project is to develop five circular economy models that focus on the recovery of waste from the paper industry so that it can subsequently be used as secondary raw materials in sectors with high raw materials consumption, such as construction, mining and the chemical industry.

With a budget of 7.8 million euro, the project is funded by European Commission Horizon 2020 Research & Development Programme. Its main aim is to unlock the potential of a resource-efficient model based on industrial symbiosis which will demonstrate the potential of the major non-hazardous waste streams generated by the pulp and paper industry (i.e. green liquor dregs, grits, lime mud, paper sludge, fly ash, deinking paper and fibre sludge) as valuable secondary raw materials. The project seeks to demonstrate the high value of this waste in three different forms: unmodified, with minimum processing and subsequent to any treatment type.

The project consortium is made up of 20 partners from five countries (Spain, Portugal, Slovenia, France and Sweden). It encompasses the entire value chain, including the academic sector, public authorities, waste producers and end users. A systemic approach is followed for each of the major sectors targeted, integrating the whole value chain from the production of waste through to its final application. In each sector, all the major stakeholders are present in the circular model, including waste producers, waste managers, end-users and different social bodies.

The five circular economy models proposed are as follows:

In the construction sector:

- *Circular economy model 1:* Recovery of causticizing residuals from the paper industry (lime mud, slaker grits and green liquor dregs) as secondary raw materials for concrete and asphalt manufacturing.
- *Circular economy model 2:* Recovery of deinking paper sludge and fly ash from paper industry energy recovery processes for the rehabilitation and slope stabilization of landslides in railway lines.
- *Circular economy model 3:* Use of fly ash from paper industry energy recovery processes as hydraulic binders for roads.

In the chemical industry:

- *Circular economy model 4:* Recovery of primary sludge from wastewater treatment for the production of ethanol derivatives.

FIGURE 30-ARTICLE PUBLISHED IN FUTUREVIRO MAGAZINE - 2019

4.2-Peer reviewed and technical

Some peer reviewed articles have been launched to index magazines, but no one has been published in the M18-M36 period.

The last quarter of the project will bring new articles concerning to the advance of the circular cases and other work packages.

5-Indicators

The main objective of the C&D activities is to reach and finally engage more relevant stakeholders into PAPERCHAIN project. The scope will aim as a priority at qualified visitors on digital formats, instead of massive visits. To estimate the evolution of C&D activities, a battery of indicators (KPIs) were designed and are being tracked during the whole project.

Due to the pandemic, some of the indicators originally planned has changed. A clear example about this is the indicator that take into account the number of attendees to the final event, that most probably will not be possible to be celebrated.

The following lines represent the way it is being measured the impacts in digital channels owned by paperChain, but it is not possible to measure the ones led by the communication departments of the consortium, that it is expected to be higher.

The final measurements of indicators will be presented at the end of the project.

5.1-Website

Website launched (initial version): 2017, October

Consortium Platform launched: 2017, the 14th of November (during General Assembly)

Updated → in a continuous way

Indicators monitored in a continuous way via Google Analytics.

KPIs reporting → at the end of every year and at the end of the project.

5.2-Social Networks

Created profiles of the project in Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, Instagram.

Communications via social networks will accompany the evolution of the demo cases.

Audience Overview

All Users
100.00% Users

1 Jan 2019 - 31 Dec 2019

Overview

Users 2,283	New Users 2,263	Sessions 3,297
Number of Sessions per User 1.44	Page Views 8,290	Pages/Session 2.51
Avg. Session Duration 00:02:22	Bounce Rate 62.72%	

Country	Users	% Users
1. Spain	519	22.62%
2. United States	451	19.66%
3. Portugal	146	6.36%
4. France	123	5.36%
5. United Kingdom	88	3.84%
6. Sweden	81	3.53%
7. Italy	66	2.88%
8. China	59	2.57%
9. Belgium	55	2.40%
10. Brazil	52	2.27%

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FIGURE 31-DATA RELATED TO VISITS TO WWW.PAPERCHAIN.EU IN 2019

Audience Overview

All Users
100.00% Users

1 Jan 2020 - 31 May 2020

Overview

Users 805	New Users 769	Sessions 1,124
Number of Sessions per User 1.40	Page Views 2,682	Pages/Session 2.39
Avg. Session Duration 00:02:11	Bounce Rate 62.81%	

■ New Visitor ■ Returning Visitor

Country	Users	% Users
1. Spain	195	24.16%
2. United States	135	16.73%
3. Portugal	64	7.93%
4. United Kingdom	41	5.08%
5. France	36	4.46%
6. Germany	32	3.97%
7. Sweden	31	3.84%
8. Belgium	25	3.10%
9. Netherlands	20	2.48%
10. India	13	1.61%

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FIGURE 32-DATA RELATED TO VISITS TO WWW.PAPERCHAIN.EU IN 2020 (31ST OF MAY)

FIGURE 33-TWITTER INDICATORS

FIGURE 34-LINKEDIN INDICATORS

6-Conclusions

The communication and dissemination strategy developed for the paperChain project has been always focused on global audiences. During the project, the consortium has participated in a large number of events of national, European and global repercussion and it is worth highlighting the recognition as the best global innovation award, given to a paper from the project at the World Road Congress held in Abu Dhabi and organised by PIARC.

A large number of specific communication materials have been developed for each of the Circular Cases, with a high quality in terms of design and content presentation. Fortunately, the approach to the materials was from the outset oriented towards digital environments, so that adaptation to the virtual world for the pandemic has been completely natural.

The approach taken for all communication and dissemination materials has always been clearly market-oriented, trying to align with the project's exploitation and replicability plans, as set out in the H2020 programme's communication and dissemination guidelines.

In this way, the consortium has worked and continue to work actively to have a greater and better impact on the dissemination of project results, highlighting those that have been identified as levers of change for the adoption of the eco-innovative solutions developed in the project. At this point, it is important to highlight the complexity of dealing with the dissemination of 5 projects in one, due to the heterogeneity of the different demonstrators, in order to achieve an individual identity and a collective communication argument.

The key agents identified at the beginning of the project have maintained their specific weight during the project, and in parallel, the results most valued by these key agents for the implementation of these new solutions have been defined and contrasted, adapting the communication and dissemination materials to these requirements.

At the time when the consortium was most active in terms of dissemination, the pandemic hit us hard. The communication and dissemination strategy in 2020 had to be rethought towards digital content, timing and formats, with the added difficulty of attracting and retaining project participants.

Likewise, the way of measuring impacts has changed significantly, although in purely digital environments it is easier to monitor, it also makes it more difficult to capture really interesting audiences, due to the over-information we have in this new reality.

In this sense, and in order to better capture, promote and retain the attention of relevant agents, we are working on the development of new communication materials for digital environments and that serve as a business card of the project, summarising the main results

and milestones achieved and framed in the needs found by the potential implementers of the solutions. Finally, it should be noted that all communication and dissemination efforts have taken into account in their different formats the average citizen of the European Union, patron of all European projects.

In the last months of the project there is a clear commitment of all partners to disseminate, communicate and promote the project and all the achievements we have reached as a consortium. We must emphasise that this has been possible largely because we have worked as an integrated team, as a family in which all members are actively collaborating to ensure that paperChain constitutes a paradigm shift in the use of waste generated by the large paper industry.

